

Role of E-Commerce in reducing operational Cost

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Abstract: E-Commerce, semiconductor, B2C, B2B, C2C, M-Commerce, electronics market, Personal Digital Assistant, marketplace, Domain Name system, trajectory, Geographical boundaries, Amazon, electronic money, penetration, demonstration, collaboration, electronic data interchange (EDI), time-based, inventory tracking levels costs, point of sale, legislations, infrastructure development, ex-chequers, AIRBNB, WTO, DTPP, OLX, unemployment, RICS, RCEP, Trade India, Google Pay, environment.

Introduction:

Day by day the entire global economy is becoming dependent on E-commerce platform. The importance of e-commerce is increasing day by day. Perhaps the entire economic transaction will run on e-commerce platform. So, Research and study on e-commerce is very important.

E-commerce (electronic commerce) is the activity of electronically buying or selling of products on online services or over the Internet. E-commerce draws on technologies such as mobile commerce, electronic funds transfer, supply chain management,

Major Types of e-Commerce

Type of e-Commerce	Example
B2C- Business to consumer	Amazon.com is a general merchandiser that sells consumer products to retail consumers.
B2B- Business to Business	Trade India is an online Business to Business (B2B) portal for small businesses based in India and around the globe
C2C – Consumer to Consumer	www.olx.in website creates a marketplace where consumers can auction or sell goods directly to other consumers.
P2P – Peer to Peer	AIRBNB is a service that lets property owners rent out their spaces to travelers looking for a place to stay, without the intervention of a market makes as in C2C Ecommerce
M-Commerce (Mobile Commerce)	Google Pay is an example of M-Commerce People use it on mobile to conduct Online financial transactions

What is meaning of B2C?

B2C stands for business-to-consumer, as in a transaction that takes place between a business and an individual as the end customer. B2C business-to-consumer ecommerce, also called retail ecommerce, is a business model that involves sales between online businesses and consumers .

A popular example of a B2C e-commerce platform is Amazon. Ecommerce sales happen almost entirely over the internet, apart from the shipping and delivery processes, so they give sellers and buyers the comfort and freedom to make transactions at any time and from any place. This increased ease of both buying and selling online, as compared to traditional

Internet marketing, online transaction processing, electronic data interchange (EDI), inventory management systems, and automated data collection systems. E-commerce is in turn driven by the technological advances of the semiconductor industry, and is the largest sector of the electronics industry.

Experts believe that: The Indian e-Commerce market is expected to reach \$170 billion by 2025. India's online shopper base is to reach nearly 500-600 million by 2030 and become the 2nd largest globally.

sales, has made B2C ecommerce one of the fastest growing sectors in the global economy

What is meaning of B2B?

In B2B stands for Business To Business, In this model one business sells a set of products or services to another business. Typically, there is a group or department that uses the vendor's products and services. Occasionally, a single user on the buyer side makes a transaction in support of the company's business goals.

One of best example of B2B ecommerce platform is Tradeindia.com in India. This website provides information about Indian and global sellers and buyers with over 12,000 product categories and sub-categories. The main products and services offered

by the portal include online business catalogs, DialB2B, Trade Alerts, Call Me Free Service, credit reports and trade leads.

What is meaning of C2C?

Customer to customer (C2C) is a business model that enables customers to trade with each other, frequently in an online environment. C2C businesses are a type of business model that emerged with e-commerce technology and the sharing economy.

<https://www.olx.in> is a website where the transactions take place between customers is known as a C2C (customer-to-customer) business. In OLX, the seller is also a customer/consumer, and the buyer is also a customer. In India, for customers it is one of secured market system for the sale of used goods or services.

What is meaning of P2P?

A peer-to-peer (P2P) service is a decentralized platform whereby two individuals interact directly with each other, without intermediation by a third party. Instead, the buyer and the seller transact directly with each other via the P2P service. The P2P platform may provide services such as search, screening, rating, payment processing, or escrow.

Airbnb website is an example of P2P E Commerce platform. This website helps to connects people who own a product or offer a service with people who want to buy or rent it. Airbnb is a classic example. The role of the website is to help these two groups of people, who find each other. The site also handles payments and helps build trust between the parties.

What is meaning of M-Commerce?

M-Commerce, also known as Mobile commerce. It is platform of buying and selling of goods and services through wireless handheld devices such as smartphones and tablets. M-commerce is a form of e-commerce that enables users to access online shopping platforms without the use of a desktop computer.

Google Pay app, Amazon Mobile app, Paytm App helps user in conducting online transactions, paying bills, sale & purchase of products, and internet banking by using wireless devices such as mobile phones, tablets, etc.

Benefits/Advantages of e-Commerce

1. Faster Buying Process
2. Helps in reducing cost.
3. Affordable advertising and Marketing.
4. Decreases the cost of paper-based information
5. Reduced the cost of communication
6. Provides richer communication than traditional means.
7. Fast delivery of digitized products.
8. Increased flexibility of location.
9. The process of e-Commerce enables sellers to come closer to customers that lead to increased productivity and perfect competition the

customer can also choose between different sellers and buy the most relevant products as per requirements, preferences and budget Moreover, customer now have access to virtual stores.

10. E-Commerce also lads to significant transaction cost reduction for consumers.
11. E-Commerce has emerged as one of the fast growing trade channel available for the cross-border trade of goods and service.
12. It provides a wider reach and reception across the global market with minimum investments. It enables sellers to sell to a global audience and also customers to make global choice. Geographical boundaries and challenges are eradicated drastically reduced
13. Through direct interaction with final customer this e-Commerce process cuts the product distribution chain to a significant extent. A direct and transparent channel between the producers made. This way product and service that are created to cater to the individual preferences of the target audience.
14. Customers can easily locate product since e-Commerce can be one store set up for all the customers' business needs.
15. Ease of doing business it makes starting managing business easy and simple.
16. The growth in the e-commerce sector can boost employment, increase revenue from export increase tax collection by ex-chequers, and provide better products and services to customers in the long-term.

Limitations of e-Commerce Disadvantages

1. Lack of system security reliability and standards.
2. Lack of privacy.
3. Insufficient bandwidth.
4. Integrating e-Commerce software with existing software is still a challenge
5. Lack of trust in 1) unknowns on the other end of the transaction 2) integrity of the transaction itself and 3) electronic money that is only bits and bytes.
6. There is lesser accountability on part of e-Commerce companies and the product quality may or may not meet the expectations of the customers.
7. It depends strongly on network connectivity and information technology. Mechanical failures can cause unpredictable effect on total process.
8. Definite legislations both domestically and internationally to regulate e-Commerce transactions are still to be framed leading to lack of regulation of the sector.
9. At times, there is a loss of privacy, culture or economic identity of the customer.

10. There is a chance of fraudulent financial transaction and loss of sensitive financial information.

Government Initiatives Regarding e-Commerce in India

1. The government has taken action to encourage the growth of more entrepreneurs on E Commerce Platform Since 2014, the government of India has introduced several new programs, including Start-up India, Skill India, Digital India, and the Innovation Fund. It is anticipated that the timely and efficient execution of these programs will contribute to the expansion of e-commerce in the country.
2. In february 2019 a draft National e-commerce policy has been prepared and placed in the public domain by Government, which addressed six broad areas of the e-commerce marketplaces, regulatory issues, infrastructure development; data stimulating domestic digital economy and export promotion through e-commerce.
3. The department of commerce initiated exercise and established a think tank on 'Framework for National policy on e-commerce and a task force under it to deliberate on the challenges confronting India in the area of the digital economy and electronic commerce.

FDI guidelines for e-commerce by DTPP -

1. In order to increase the participation of foreign players in the e-commerce field, the Government has increased the limit of foreign direct investment (FDI) in the e-commerce marketplace model for up to 100% in B2B model.
2. Government e-marketplace signed a memorandum of understanding with Union Bank of India to facilitate a cashless paperless and transparent payment system for an array of services in October 2019.
3. The heavy investment of Government of India in ralling out the fiber network for 5G will help boost e-commerce in India.
4. In the Union Budget of 2018-19, the Government has allocated ₹ 8,000 crore to Bharat Net Project to provide broadband services to 1,50,000 gram panchayat

Way Ahead

1. E-commerce has become an important part of many multilateral negotiations such Regional Comprehensive Economic partnership (RCEP), WTO, RICS etc.
2. E-commerce still faces various issues like international trade, domestic trade, competition policy, Consumer protection, information technology etc. As a growing sector with huge interest from both domestic and international players it becomes pertinent to regulate it

keeping in mind the interest of both entrepreneurs and consumers. A conducive encouraged level playing field should be encouraged.

3. Policy makers should be also be mindful of sharpening a vibrant domestic industry. A comprehensive policy is of utmost importance to reflect India's position in both domestic and international or multilateral forums.

Objective

1. To check that the commercial sector has increased due to e-commerce.
2. To find out whether operational value is reduced due to e-commerce or not.
3. To find out whether e-commerce has made doing business easier or not
4. To check whether India's GDP rate has increased due to e-commerce or not.
5. To find out that companies doing online business are getting huge profit in business.

Hypothesis

1. E-commerce has reduced the opportunity cost.
2. E-Commerce has made doing business easier.
3. E-commerce makes trading less time consuming
4. E-commerce has connected many buyers and sellers to each other.
5. E-commerce has reduced the cost value.

Research Methodology

The following instruments have been used as research methods for the above topic.

1. Article's published so far related to the above topic.
2. Information released directly and indirectly by the government so far according to the above topic.
3. Articles' published so far the above topic in newspapers, Magazines weekly.
4. According to the above topic so far, internet articles posted by different websites famous authors.

According to the above topic the published articles information, information released by the government as well as various articles were verified to write on this topic. The essay has been after reading meditating and extensive study of various writings.

Conclusion

1. E-commerce has seen an increase in trade.
2. Due to e-commerce business is going at a fast pace.
3. Online trading has increased due to e-commerce.
4. E-commerce has made people prefer to buy things online.

5. E-commerce has made it easy to start a business with very little money.
6. Virtual stores are gaining popularity.
7. Du to e-commerce the seller has succeeded in delivering the products of the customers very close interest.
8. The e-commerce market place model sees increased foreign investment limits.
9. E-commerce business has increased productivity.
10. E-commerce makes all transaction paperless and cashless.
11. Boosting exports by increasing taxes on e-commerce.
12. E-commerce a generate employment and provide better service to customers in the long run.
13. Consumers can get their required items at their doorstep. Thanks to e-commerce.
14. E-commerce is creating a paperless world.
15. E-commerce is a starting to reveal the secrets of private life.
16. It is observed that e-commerce can be dangerous in dealing with people online.
17. Paper cost has started to come down because of E Commerce.
18. E-commerce has also shown that goods and services can be shipped across borders very quickly.
19. It appears that e-commerce transactions cannot be trusted immediately.
20. E-commerce focuses only on electronic money.

Recommendations.

1. The government should implement a specific mechanism to make the common people believe on e-commerce.
2. All people should be trained to do e-commerce transaction.
3. Care should be taken to ensure that the consumer's private life is not disturbed during e-commerce transactions.
4. The young generation should eagerly enter this field of c-commerce and embrace self-employment.
5. India can definitely be able to become the number one unemployment free country in the world if the young generation eagerly jumps into the field of e-commerce.

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